

Environmental Marine Information System (EMIS)

A geo-portal to assist in the management of European seas and global ocean

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Marine Analyst

Figure 2. The EMIS Web-GIS application is based on a MapServer engine, an open source geographic data delivering engine with integrated GDAL (Geospatial Data Abstraction Library), originally developed by the University of Minnesota (UMN), for building spatially enabled web applications. UMN MapServer (v.6.4) allows creating geographic image maps, as well as to browse and query the database.

Figure 7. Chlorophyll concentration average seasonal decomposition graphics and statistical analysis (not shown) (ref: Vantropotte, V. Melin, F. Temporal variability of 10-year global SeaWiFS time-series of phytoplankton chlorophyll a concentration ICES J. Mar. Sci., 2009, 66, 1547-1556.)

http://.../webservices/4km/wcs-t?TIME=2016-01&service=wcs&version=1.0.0&request=getcoverage&coverage=GMIS_A_CHLA&crs=EPSG:4326&BBOX=-31,-51,61,41&format=image/tiff&interpolation=nearest

Figure 12. INSPIRE OGC Web Coverage Service supporting time dimension (WCS-time ISO 8601:1988(E))

Figure 8. Local map of seabed habitats obtained by aggregation of two sources of information: EUMS seafloor habitat classes and UNEP's Global seafloor Geomorphic features map, as described in Tempera (2015).

To ensure full interoperability with other GIS systems, EMIS is implemented with Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)-compliant services and INSPIRE standards (EC 2007). In particular, OGC Web Coverage Service (fig. 12) and its tiling scheme facilitate the publication and exchange of geospatial data with space and time-varying features. Moreover, EMIS is compliant with the EU programme on interoperability solutions and common framework for European public administrations, businesses and citizens (ISA² Programme; EU 2015), which supports the development of digital solutions allowing interoperable cross-border and cross-sector public services.

Introduction

The Environmental Marine Information System (EMIS) has been developed as part of the European Commission – Joint Research Centre contribution to the Europe 2020 objectives of a “smart, sustainable and inclusive growth”. Through the analysis of satellite data and modeling outputs, illustrated by a case study of a marine protected area in the Mediterranean Sea (i.e. “Bouches de Bonifacio” WDPA ID 178271),

Figure 3. 3D-viewing of the local bathymetry within and around the marine protected area “Bouches de Bonifacio, Iles des Moines”.

Figure 9. Density of alien species within and in the vicinity of the Bonifacio marine protected area. Data are extracted from the European Alien Species Information Network (EASIN).

Another feature of the Marine Analyst is given in terms of alien species occurring in the MPA (fig. 9) which are automatically extracted from the European Alien Species Information network (EASIN). This network maintains an inventory of all known alien and cryptogenic species in Europe as required by the Convention on Biological Diversity and EU regulation on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species. A range number of alien species is given on a 10x10 km grid, with the species name possibly occurring in the studied area. For the Bonifacio MPA (fig.9), alien species are listed as: *Asterionellopsis glacialis*, *Atherina boyeri*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Haliotis tuberculata*, *Hexaplex trunculus*, *Potamopyrgus antipodarum*, *Prorocentrum minimum*, *P. triestinum*.

the poster highlights the benefits of EMIS for Member States and other bodies as a tool to support an effective and long-lasting stewardship of EU seas. EMIS marine analyst report provides scientific and technical value-added products to assist Member States and other bodies with cost-effective monitoring and comparable assessment of environmental status of their marine waters.

Figure 4. Time-series of monthly sea surface temperature (SST, in °C) as derived from MODIS-Terra sensor for the period 2005-2015.

Figure 10. Maps of monthly sea surface temperature anomalies with respect to monthly climatology calculated over the full MODIS-Terra time series as available in EMIS.

Figures 4 & 5 show maps of monthly SST (fig. 4 from MODIS-Terra) and chlorophyll time series (fig. 5 from MODIS-Aqua) for the last decadal period 2005-2015 at 4 km resolution. The seasonal variability of both variables is highly visible on these maps with maximum SST in July and August coinciding with minimum concentrations of surface chlorophyll content. Maximum chlorophyll concentrations are observed in March with a growing period lasting all winter months. For the entire time-series, mean values for SST and Chla over the entire period are 18.28 ± 4.27 °C and 0.32 ± 0.27 mg.m⁻³, respectively.

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Figure 1. Local map of the protected area “Bouches de Bonifacio, Iles des Moines”. The area is 100% marine located at the southern tip of Corsica and includes waters surrounding the small islands “Ilots des Moines”.

The area is part of the Bonifacio Strait between Corsica and Sardinia distant of 16 km. Maximum water depth in the central part of the Strait is 100 m, but increasing rapidly on the west side to few thousands meters. The marine Analyst report includes 2-D (not shown) and 3D bathymetry maps of the area (fig. 3), created from the 2016 release of EMODnet DTM product covering European seas at ca. 230 m grid resolution. The 3-D maps are given in 4 different perspectives (only 1 shown here), enabling a better vision of the topography on either side of the MPA.

Figure 5. Time-series of monthly chlorophyll a concentration (in mg.m⁻³) as derived from the sensor MODIS-Aqua for the period 2005-2015.

Figure 6. Monthly climatology of modeled bottom salinity around the BBIM marine protected area.

The analysis of the surface variables observed from satellite is complemented with outcomes of 3D hydrodynamic model describing the water column and bottom physics. For example, monthly climatological values of the bottom salinity (fig.6) and bottom temperature (not shown) are estimated over a decade period using the freely available General Estuarine Transport Model (GETM). The variability of these physical parameters is important to evaluate the status of benthic ecosystems within the protected area.

Conclusion

The Environmental Marine Information System (EMIS) has features and components that are specifically dedicated to assisting in the management of marine and coastal waters in Europe and globally. The system provides an interoperable spatial data infrastructure platform able to integrate and disseminate the different spatial and referenced datasets and services in a standardized way. The system supplies the users with: i) continuous, detailed and accurate marine/coastal environmental data as derived from satellite observations (ocean colour, sea surface temperature) and model outputs (bathymetry, hydrodynamics, habitats); ii) indicators for the diagnosis of the coastal state and analyses of changes in marine ecosystems (anomalies); iii) basic navigation and interrogation tools with elemental statistics and time-series analysis. EMIS has the merit to actively support the implementation of the EU marine directive as this system provides geo-spatial data that contribute to suitably describe and monitor the environmental status of European Seas. Moreover, the EMIS Marine Analyst, built around the R programming language, has been developed to locally explore the EMIS marine database, restrict the data extraction to the selected area of interest and a defined time period, and perform data analysis and indicator computation on-the-fly. The tool was optimized for a large community of users and operates in a simple way as long as internet access is available.